

CALIPER
Gender Equality in STEM Research

Linking Research & Innovation for Gender Equality

D3.4 Final GEPs

WP3 – Implementation of GEPs

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Executive Summary

The report presents the new/refined versions of the tailored and inclusive GEPs (Gender Equality Plans) elaborated by the consortium's partners to foster inclusive institutional change for gender equality in their organizations.

The elaboration of the new/refined GEPs represent the last step of a process started in:

- WP2 Design and Development of customized GEPs (CALIPER GEPs) in which the co-creation process started involving the CALIPER partners and their internal and external stakeholders for the development of the CALIPER tailored and inclusive GEPs,
- WP3 Implementation of GEPs in which the tailored and inclusive GEPs implemented in the partner organisations in two iteration phases,
- WP4 Monitoring and Evaluation, in which the the tailored and inclusive GEPs followed up in order to benchmark their results against the set goals and objectives
- WP5 Engagement, chane management and sustainability, in which several internal and external communication activities organized by the partners in order to diffuse the knowledge related to the GEPs implementation process to the interested stakeholders.

It should be noted that:

- 2 inclusive GEPs (by UNILE and UZG FER) will continue their implementation since their overall duration exceeded the CALIPER project life cycle without being changed. Therefore, there is no need to undergo any approval procedure.
- 2 inclusive GEPs (by YU and IRB) have been updated after the 2nd iteration of the GEP implementation. Both GEPs are approved by their internal administration (for IRB it was not necessary for the updated GEP to undergo a new approval process).
- 4 new inclusive GEPs have been elaborated (by ECE NTUA, SNRFSFG, UEFISCDI, STU BA) after the 2nd iteration of the GEPs implementation. The GEPs have been subjected to internal approval by the respective internal authority. Three out of four GEPs have been approved. There still 1 which is still under the approval process (ECE NTUA).
- Parts of 1 inclusive GEP (by ULB) that has been elaborated within CALIPER will be incorporated in the institutional overall Gender and Diversity Plan. At the time this report is being elaborated, the plan is under consultation.

In these new or updated inclusive GEPs, 72 actions have been included in the different areas of intervention (human resources, institutional governance, research/research funding, teaching, transfer to market, communication, students service, sexual harassment). This numbers sums up the actions included in the new GEPs (ECE NTUA, SNRFSFG, UEFISCDI, STU BA) and to the updated GEPs (YU and IRB)

Chapter 2 shows an overview of the actions included in all inclusive GEPs, trying to point out some emerging trends and commonalities within the consortium. Overall, all the areas of intervention have been addressed by GEPs actions, with clear differences between RPOs and RFOs. The analysis shows how the areas which have been addressed at most are the ones of human resources and institutional communication.

Chapters from 3 onward present a summarized description of the partners' GEPs. These individual chapters contain a link to the full versions of the GEPs (when applicable), collected in an online [repository](#) that is constantly updated as the final approval of the GEPs by the appointed institutions' authorities takes place.

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1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose, scope, structure of the deliverable

The CALIPER project supports 7 RPOs and 2 RFO in the development, implementation, and sustainability of their tailored and inclusive GEPs. *WP3 Implementation of GEPs* supported the implementation of the GEPs previously developed in *WP2 Design and Development of Customised GEPs (CALIPER GEPs)*. GEPs have been implemented in two iterative implementation phases [M18-M30 and M32-M44] to achieve institutional change for gender equality as defined by each RPO/RFO in *T2.3 GEPs Design and Development*. After the end of each iteration phase, the results have been analysed through Key Performance Indicators leading to the redesign and refinement of the GEPs. The present document collects the final GEPs that have been elaborated by the 9 partner organizations also taking into account the evaluation and monitoring activities performed under *WP4 Monitoring and evaluation* and the activities carried out in *WP5 Engagement, change management and sustainability* to ensure the sustainability of the actions.

The following partners are the GEP implementing partners of the CALIPER project:

- RPOs: IRB, ECE NTUA, STU BA, ULB, UNILE, UZG, YU.
- RFOs: UEFISCDI, SRNSFG.

As a result of the two implementation phases, and based on the analysis of each individual GEP implementation and sustainability process:

- 2 inclusive GEPs (by UNILE and UZG FER) will continue their implementation since their overall duration exceeded the CALIPER project life cycle without being changed. Therefore, there is no need to undergo any approval procedure.
- 2 inclusive GEPs (by YU and IRB) have been updated after the 2nd iteration of the GEP implementation. Both GEPs are approved by their internal administration (for IRB it was not necessary for the updated GEP to undergo a new approval process).
- 4 new inclusive GEPs have been elaborated (by ECE NTUA, SRNSFG, UEFISCDI, STUBA) after the 2nd iteration of the GEPs implementation. The GEPs have been subjected to internal approval by the respective internal authority. Three out of four GEPs have been approved. The last one is still under the approval process (ECE NTUA).
- Parts of 1 inclusive GEP (by ULB) that has been elaborated within CALIPER will be incorporated in the institutional overall Gender and Diversity Plan. At the time this report is being elaborated, the plan is under consultation.

1.2 Structure of the deliverable

The deliverable is structured with an initial chapter introducing the scope, structure and the relation to other WPs and Tasks. Chapter 2 gives an overview of the inclusive GEPs' actions and the respective thematic areas. From Chapter 3 to Chapter 11, the inclusive GEPs are described, and where applicable the links where to find the full version of the GEPs are provided. A final chapter with concluding remarks is also included.

1.3 Relation to other WPs & Tasks

This deliverable is the second deliverable of *T3.3 GEPs Implementation in Each RPO/ RFO – 2nd Iteration of WP3 Implementation of GEPs*. WP3 is strictly connected with *WP4 Monitoring and Evaluation*, since

monitoring and evaluation activities are based on the actions implemented within WP3. In addition, the GEPs implementation process has been supported by activities within WP5 *Engagement, Change Management and Sustainability* and WP6 *Dissemination and Communication*.

2 GEP overview and main areas of interventions

The present report presents the 2 refined/updated GEPs (by YU and IRB) (for more information please see D3.3 Mini reports on the redesign and refinements elements in each RPO/RFO v2), 4 new GEPs (by ECE NTUA, SNRSFG, UEFISCDI, STU BA) and the strategic objectives to be incorporated in ULB's institutional Gender and Diversity Plan as they have been developed/defined at the end of the 2nd iteration phase of the GEPs implementation. In addition, for consistency, it presents also the 2 GEPs (by UNILE and UZG FER) which have been developed during the CALIPER project and their duration exceed the project's lifecycle and which continue without any changes until their end.

The new/refined GEPs developed by the partners and presented in this report vary in terms of duration. The minimum duration is 1 year (see UEFISCDI) and the maximum duration is 3 years (SNRSFG). The duration for each GEP was based on the partners' internal gender equality objectives and procedures in place.

The actions introduced in the new GEPs are organized based on the areas of intervention listed below, which were introduced in D1.1 "Internal and external assessment methodologies and guidelines".

Area/topic of intervention	Description
Human resources	It includes units/departments in charge of recruitment/retention & career progression and work-life balance/wellbeing services or provisions.
Institutional governance	This area is mainly related to the decision-making structures and bodies as well as governance processes featuring each organization.
Institutional communication	It concerns the use of gender sensitive language in the organization's documents as well as in the communication channels and materials.
Research + Research funding	This area refers to integrating gender into the content of research within all scientific fields and components (design, delivery and research communication). It represents the core activity of Research Funding Organizations, encompassing processes of preparing calls for proposals and setting evaluation criteria, to organizing evaluation processes leading to selections and decisions on funding allocation.
Students services	It mainly consisting in students' recruitment and post graduate counselling.
Teaching	It is related to curricula design and preparation, but also includes interaction and communication with students as well students' assessment/evaluation activities in order to understand whether gender bias is present at any stages.
Transfer to market (or third mission)	This area concerns the role of research institution to engage with societal needs and market demands by linking its activities with its own socio-economic context.

Sexual harassment	It is related to the existence of actions and policies aimed at addressing and preventing sexual harassment and gender-based violence in the organization.
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Table 1 Areas of intervention

Overall, partners have inserted 72 actions in their new GEPs (see figure 1 below). This figure and the analysis below concern only the actions included in the GEPs of YU, IRB, ECE NTUA, SNRFSFG, UEFISCDI, STU BA since these parnters developed their new GEP or updated their current ones. The actions included in UNILE and UZG FER’s GEPs have been included and analysed in previous deliverables under WP2 and WP3 such as D2.3 GEPs and D3.1 GEPs implementation during phase 1.

The areas in which partners have included more actions are institutional governance and institutional communicaton, with 12 actions respectively. This is not surprising since both areas together with the one of human resources were the ones counting more actions even in the previous version of GEPs. In addition, the human resource area can also be considered as the most encompassing one, considered it includes different sub-topics (e.g. recruitment and selection, working conditions and work-life balance, career progression, etc.).

Also, the area of research and research funding counts a notable share of actions with 12 actons respectively. Here it can be noticed that many actions listed under the research/reaserch funding area belong to the RFOs of the CALIPER consortium.

On the other side, the areas with less actions are teaching/student services with 5 actions and Sexual harassment with 7 actions.

Research/research funding is the areas in which all partners have included at least one action.

Figure 1 Overall gender equality actions per thematic area

3 ULB's GEP

As it has been mentioned earlier in this document, parts of the ULB's CALIPER GEP will be integrated into the central Gender & Diversity planning of the institution.

The following serves as a strategic note explaining how goals, objectives, and results of the CALIPER GEP will be carried forward in a long-term perspective to guarantee sustainable impact beyond the project period of CALIPER, by the integration into central G&D [Gender and Diversity] planning and policy objectives at institutional level.

It is important to remark that at the initial conceptualisation phase of the GEP in 2020, the successful strategy was pursued to embed the GEP into central ambitions in the area of gender and diversity, in order to ensure longevity, institutional legitimisation and support from the get-go. Indeed, ULB had already institutionalized the gender equality policy by entrusting this responsibility to a vice-rector back in 2012, extended to gender and diversity policy from 2016.

ULB's participation in CALIPER was initiated by the previous Vice-rector in charge of the gender and diversity policy of the university. Of note, [a diversity plan](#) for working staff (2019-2022), supported by ACTIRIS, the employment agency for the Brussels Region, was ongoing at the time CALIPER was launched. Thus, [a link](#) to the central gender and diversity plan and policy in place during that period (2020), had been built into the design of the CALIPER GEP from the start of the project.

Four years down the line, CALIPER's project period has concluded and key achievements as well as learnings can now be harnessed. CALIPER and its inclusive GEP have been a pioneer project, an excellent learning laboratory for designing and implementing gender equality work and a testing ground for future impact, helping to lay the ground-work and preparatory actions for long term change. These advances can now be developed to benefit the wider stakeholder community of the university and across other faculties.

A reversed strategic process will be applied, where key objectives, goals and most successful approaches of the GEP can now be transferred into the new central strategic G&D plan, that is currently in development. Thus, closing the (learning) loop and ensuring continuation and durability of gender equality work that has been performed during the time of Caliper.

Moreover, the new plan would adopt a "gender inclusive approach", by addressing other sources of inequalities (such as handicap, ethnic origins, age) and their intersection with gender.

The CALIPER project targeted change in R&I fields with a strong underrepresentation of women and the GEP was thus devised to particularly make an impact in the STEM fields and faculties, but also included (both soft and structural) objectives and actions relevant at an institution wide level that target gender inequalities that are common to all disciplines. Thus, a set of key objectives in the CALIPER GEP will now be carried forward into the new central G&D plan in two ways. On the one hand, a select set of "STEM specific objectives" will be represented and, on the other hand, certain "transversal objectives" with institution wide relevance will be integrated.

With this strategy the new central G&D plan will include 'STEM specific dimensions' – that focus on making a tangible impact to tackle the underrepresentation of women in these fields. The strategy will include soft actions to fight gender stereotypes in STEM (e.g. linked to learning from the WIN Event, role model campaigns, training on the gender dimension for secondary school science teachers, gender sensitive STEM outreach) and to integrate the gender dimension in STEM research and teaching (e.g. integration of a gender+ and diversity perspective into STEM teaching profile and competency frameworks) will be

continued, as well as structural actions to redress specifically gender inequalities in STEM careers at university, with the continuation of the feasibility study on affirmative actions carried out in the CALIPER inclusive GEP .

On the other hand, the plan carries forward ‘overarching/transversal measures’ including (but not exclusively) – preventive measures on sexual and/or discriminatory harassment and violence, as well as other types of discrimination; continues the combat against stereotypes and biases; fosters inclusive communications; promotes inclusive pedagogy and gender competences in teaching; advances the gender dimension in research; and of course pursues goals to bridge the leaky pipeline, to help equal the scales for women in their career progression [recruitment, promotion, retention, maternity leaves, etc.]. These objectives will be applied to impact across the whole institution and diverse faculties, for instance, by - evaluating the pilot project on gender-balance in advisory boards and extending the measure to more boards; by implementing new measures for work-life balance that draw on the feasibility studies carried out in the CALIPER GEP; by disseminating widely the Toolkit for gender sensitive recruitment, and by organizing more trainings (on sexism and sexual harassment, inclusive communication...).

Moreover, the design of the GEP has ensured that a set of actions secure a level of permanent change. Gender+ Commissions that have been established in both STEM faculties, as official bodies and action-oriented WGs, who will carry their work forward – and each commission has a set of priorities linked to the GEP as well as independently defined measures according to the unique needs of their faculty, which they will keep working on. Thus, longevity of gender equality work here has been institutionalised and secured also at STEM Fac. Level.

Moreover, permanent actions such as the ‘gender target in STEM Phd juries’ as well as the dedicated webpages for the gender+ measures in STEM faculties, and the institution wide permanent poster campaign for sexual harassment and violence protocols/services, guarantee the stability of GEP actions in those areas.

The new central G&D plan will follow a unique strategy and structure, that integrates key learnings and goals of Caliper’s GEP, combined with university wide objectives that have been defined at institutional level. Thus, the new G&D plan works around a set of key objectives that can be operationalised to impact the institution as well as the STEM specific level.

This renewed central plan will serve to advance in the long run the universities values and policy on gender, diversity and inclusion across the whole of the community and its affiliated stakeholders from a gender inclusive approach.

This process is still undergoing. The ULB’s inclusive GEP that has been developed within the project duration can be found [here](#).

4 IRB's GEP

IRB's inclusive GEP has been refined (for more information please see D3.3 Mini reports on the redesign and refinements elements in each RPO/RFO v2) and will be valid until the end of 2024. There is no need to undergo an approval process. The updated version of the GEP can be found [here](#) and in the CALIPER project [website](#).

Overall, it includes 25 actions, grouped into the 7 areas of intervention:

Thematic area	No of Actions
Human Resources	7
Institutional Governance	5
Institutional Communication	5
Research	2
Young Scientists	2
Addressing Gender and Sexual Harassment	2
Transfer to Market	2

Table 2 IRB inclusive GEP priority areas

Below a detailed table including each action per thematic area is included with their status of implementation.

AREA OF IMPLEMENTATION	ACTION	STATUS
1 Human Resources	Review, update and disseminate existing recruitment policies and guidelines, assuring that the documentation has a gender-sensitive approach	Finalized
2 Institutional Communication	Give internal and external visibility to the new Gender Equality Plan	Finalized
3 Sexual and Gender Harassment	Review and update protocol on Sexual Harassment	Finalized
4 Institutional Governance	Develop mentoring programmes to promote career progression	Finalized
5 Institutional Governance	Consolidate and disseminate Group Leader Selection Protocol	Finalized
6 Institutional Communication	Promote institutional engagement in equality and diversity topics (videos, institutional equality day, printed materials, among others)	Finalized
7 Human Resources	Conduct a salary audit regarding equal pay	Finalized
8 Young Scientist (student services)	Reinforce equality and diversity topics in onboarding sessions	Finalized
9 Transfer to Market	Collaborative action n. 3: WIN event	Finalized
10 Institutional Communication	Organise and participate in advanced training on inclusive language	Finalized
11 Institutional Governance	Prepare an internal regulations to govern the Equality and Diversity Committee	Finalized
12 Sexual and Gender Harassment	Develop internal training on Sexual and Gender Harassment	Finalized
13 Institutional Communication	Creation and promotion of a manual/guidelines on inclusive language (English, Spanish, and Catalan)	Finalized
14 Institutional Governance	Prepare an action plan to prepare training statistics with data disaggregated by gender	Finalized
15 Human Resources	Develop a Parental Leave Guide	In progress
16 Research	Create and consolidate a protocol for planning and developing internal seminars, ensuring the participation of female speakers	In progress
17 Human Resources	Develop a Work-Life Balance Guide	In progress
18 Human Resources	Plan and develop training actions to raise awareness of the importance of work-life balance and implement a pro-conciliation leadership management model	2023-2024
19 Human Resources	Develop awareness campaigns on Intersectionality	2023-2024
20 Institutional Governance	Organise an advanced training session on gender and diversity topics for members of the Equality Commission	2023-2024
21 Research	Training sessions on the integration of the gender dimension into research	2023-2024
22 Institutional Communication	Develop checklist/guidelines for posting and checking material on institutional social media channels	2023-2024
23 Young Scientist (student services)	Integrate gender perspective training in transversal PhD programme	2023-2024
24 Human Resources	Collaborative action n. 1: Introduce measures to avoid bias in selection and evaluation processes (TBD)	2023-2024
25 Transfer to Market	Collaborative action n. 2: Develop a system to monitor the evolution of women in transfer to market (TBD)	2023-2024

Table 3 IRB's inclusive GEP actions and timeline

5 UNILE's GEP

UNILE's GEP was activated in 2022 and will be valid until 2025. UNILE's GEP can be found [here](#) and in the CALIPER project [website](#).

Overall, it includes 15 actions, grouped into the below 6 priority areas:

Thematic area	No of Actions
Human Resources	5
Gender balance in tops positions and decision-making bodies	2
Gender equality in recruitment and career advancement	3
Gender dimension in research and teaching and third mission	2
Gender prejudices and stereotypes, sexism and sexual harassment	1
Institutional communication	2

Table 4 UNILE inclusive GEP priority areas

Below a detailed table including each action per thematic area is presented.

Thematic area	Actions
Human Resources	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Promotion of inclusive culture and practices in the academic community 2. Promotion of gender diversity in the study of STEM disciplines 3. Enhancing gender diversity: Actions to ensure inclusion and well-being of male and female students 4. Identification, development and implementation of smart working actions and teleworking 5. Identification, development and implementation of actions aimed at reconciliation of life/work, valorisation of the individual worker's well-being also with regard to his or her care responsibilities
Gender balance in tops positions and decision-making bodies	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 6. Monitoring and coordination for the evaluation of gender equality at institutional level 7. Governance interventions to increase equitable visibility and representativeness
Gender equality in recruitment and career advancement	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 8. Actions for young female researchers to combat drop-out and abandonment careers 9. Support for equal opportunities in careers 10. Enhancement of gender diversity in technical-administrative careers through

	seminars, training courses and reward systems.
Gender dimension in research and teaching and third mission	11. Consolidation of gender perspective within teaching and research 12. Relations with territory and national and international actors, creation and strengthening networks, resources and design
Gender prejudices and stereotypes, sexism and sexual harassment	13. Preventing and combating bullying, harassment, discrimination and conflict in the workplace study and work relations
Institutional communication	14. Updating the gender policy webpage 15. Promote the use of inclusive language

Table 5 UNILE's inclusive GEP actions

After 2025 there will be another consultation phase for developing a new Inclusive GEP followed by an approval process.

This is fully in line with UNILE's sustainability plan (adopted and approved this year).

Some actions were introduced in the University Strategic Plan. Actions that directly affect departments fall under their individual strategic plans.

UNILE is committed to introduce recurring and ongoing actions new GEP that will be developed after the end of the current one (2025 onwards). For example, these actions may include the gender balance sheet (be updated every two years), interdisciplinary seminar cycles, courses against gender-based violence, study awards and scholarships, smart and teleworking calls, support allowances for access to kindergartens, maintenance of the healthcare facility.

Actions that have required more effort and need further support will be strengthened: a specific budget will be provided for these actions (e.g., career Alias, which requires CINECA's intervention).

6 FER UZG's GEP

The GEP elaborated by the Faculty of Electrical Engineering and Computing of the University of Zagreb in Croatia (FER UZG) for the period 2021 – 2025 has been officially approved by the decision-making bodies of the Faculty during the first iteration phase of the GEPs implementation within the project. The procedure of approval of the Gender Equality Plan underwent two main steps:

1. approval from the Dean,
2. approval from the Faculty Council.

FER UZG GEP can be found [here and](#) in the CALIPER project [website](#).

Overall, it includes 14 actions, grouped into the below 6 priority areas:

Thematic area	No of Actions
Human Resources	2
Institutional management	3
Institutional Communication	2
Teaching and Research	4
Student services	2
Sexism and Sexual Harassment	1

Table 6 FER UZG inclusive GEP priority areas

Below a detailed table including each action per thematic area is presented.

Area	Measures
Human Resources	2.1 Strengthening the availability of existing policies and services for staff 2.2 Attracting and retaining female researchers
Institutional management	3.1 Establishment of a gender equality body 3.2 Reporting on the status of gender equality 3.3 Pilot programme to strengthen the role of female researchers
Institutional communication	4.1 Establishment of a dedicated digital communication channel 4.2 Gender-sensitive language in legal documents
Teaching and research	5.1 Integration of the gender dimension in teaching 5.2 Promotion campaign for the integration of the gender dimension in research 5.3 Support for researchers after leave 5.4 Promotion of the principle of gender equality in technology transfer
Student services	6.1 Improving the availability of existing student services 6.2 Attracting new female students to the Faculty
Sexism and sexual harassment	7.1 Strengthening the system to combat sexual harassment and discrimination

Table 7 FER UZG's inclusive GEP actions

On July 23rd 2021 the document has been approved by the Dean. After the approval by the Dean, the draft underwent a public discussion before seeking approval from the Faculty Council. The draft was disseminated to all employees, and they had the opportunity to familiarize themselves with the content of the draft.

During a month-long public discussion, all employees of FER had the opportunity to provide their suggestions and comments on the draft to the faculty management. Each received suggestion was taken into consideration and addressed. At its 710th meeting on 15 September 2021, the Faculty Council adopted the Gender Equality Plan for the period 2021-2025.

7 YASAR's GEP

YU inclusive GEP has been refined (for more information please see D3.3 Mini reports on the redesign and refinements elements in each RPO/RFO v2), and already approved by the Rectorate the Board of Trustees.

The duration of the GEP is indefinite since the Gender Equality Plan of the YU has become a permanent document including actions to be implemented continuously.

Furthermore, gender equality has been included in the Strategic Plan of the university under societal contribution and social sustainability objectives for the period of 2020-2025. Also, an institutional gender equality policy is adopted.

The updated version of the GEP can be found [here and](#) in the CALIPER project [website](#).

Overall, it includes 11 actions, grouped into the below 6 priority areas:

Thematic area	No of Actions
Human Resources	2
Institutional governance	3
Institutional Communication	1
Research	2
Teaching	1
Sexual Harassment and Gender-based violence	2

Table 8 YU inclusive GEP priority areas

Below a detailed table including each action per thematic area is presented.

Thematic area	Actions
Human Resources	1. Gender Equality in Recruitment and Career Progression 2. Awareness-Raising and Empowerment Actions
Institutional governance	3. Gender equality body 4. Gender-disaggregated data collection 5. Gender equality policy
Institutional Communication	6. Gender sensitive institutional communication guidelines & trainings
Research	7. Integration of gender into institutional strategic plan 8. Diversity Research Group
Teaching	9. Gender sensitive teaching guidelines & trainings
Sexual Harassment and Gender-based violence	10. Institutional policy against sexual harassment and gender-based violence 11. Gender-based discrimination, violence and sexual harassment prevention unit

Table 9 YU's inclusive GEP actions

8 MTF STU's GEP

STU BA inclusive new GEP has been drafted and is approved by the internal management. The new GEP is foreseen to be implemented from 2024 until 2026.

The new version of the GEP can be found [here](#). It will be uploaded in the CALIPER website upon its approval and will be accessible via this [link](#).

Overall, it includes 11 actions, grouped into the below 7 priority areas:

Thematic area	No of Actions
Human Resources	1
Institutional governance	3
Institutional Communication	2
Research and teaching	2
Transfer to market	1
Sexual Harassment and Gender-based violence	1
Student services	1

Table 10 STU BA inclusive GEP priority areas

Below a detailed table including each action per thematic area is presented.

Thematic area	Actions
Human Resources	1. Addition of statistical reporting and examination of the ratio of the variable component of remuneration for women to the amount of remuneration for men in the same job positions.
Institutional governance	2. Linkage of the STU strategy to the individual NEW GEP 3. Monitoring and Evaluation Plan 4. GEP creation for the period 2027 - 2029
Institutional Communication	5. Incorporation of gender equality into the perception of affected subjects in communication. 6. Transparent audit of communication strategy.
Research and teaching	7. Perception of Gender equality by students. 8. Advisory ambassador in GE in Research
Transfer to market	9. Sustainability and Maintenance of R & I HUB.
Sexual Harassment and Gender-based violence	10. An event devoted to attracting girls to study at the Faculty.
Student services	11. Mandatory training of a selected group of internal stakeholders in the matter of GBV prevention

Table 11 STU BA's inclusive GEP actions

9 ECE NTUA's GEP

ECE NTUA inclusive new GEP has been drafted and is currently under the approval process. The new GEP is foreseen to be implemented from 2024 until 2026.

The new version of the GEP can be found [here](#). It will be uploaded in the CALIPER website upon its approval and will be accessible via this [link](#).

Overall, it includes 11 actions, grouped into the below 7 priority areas:

Thematic area	No of Actions
Human Resources	1
Institutional governance	2
Institutional Communication	3
Research	1
Teaching	1
Transfer to market	2
Sexual Harassment and Gender-based violence	1

Table 12 ECE NTUA inclusive GEP priority areas

Below a detailed table including each action per thematic area is presented.

Thematic area	Actions
Human Resources	1. Monitor the Internal indicators and targets for the representation of women
Institutional governance	2. Gender Equality Committee 3. Collection of Data on Gender Equality and on Intersectionality
Institutional Communication	4. Support the application of the "Guide of using non-sexist language in administrative documents" 5. Engagement of Role models and dissemination activities 6. Information Days and Training Workshops on gender issues in STEM
Research	7. Monitor indicators and targets for the integration of the gender dimension in research
Teaching	8. Integration of gender-related topics in selected courses and lectures
Transfer to market	9. Integration of the gender dimension in the Alumni Network 10. Cooperation with the G-WISE network
Sexual Harassment and Gender-based violence	11. Application of the mechanism dealing with cases of sexual harassment and gender-based violence

Table 13 ECE NTUA's inclusive GEP actions

10 UEFISCDI's GEP

UEFISCDI inclusive new GEP has been drafted and has been approved by its administration. The inclusive GEP is foreseen to be implemented in 2024.

The new version of the GEP can be found [here and](#) in the CALIPER project [website](#).

Overall, it includes 7 actions, grouped into the below 3 priority areas:

Thematic area	No of Actions
Research (funding)	2
Addressing Gender and Sexual Harassment	1
Transfer to Market	4

Table 14 UEFISCDI inclusive GEP priority areas

Below a detailed table including each action per thematic area is presented.

Thematic area	Actions
Research (funding)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Establishing Guidelines for Gender Dimension in Research 2. Enhancing Evaluator Expertise in Gender Equality
Addressing Gender and Sexual Harassment	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 3. Zero-Tolerance Policy Against Gender-Based Violence
Transfer to Market	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 4. Promotion of Benchmark Results from Genderactionplus project (GA+) 5. Building Stakeholder Capacity for Gender Equality 6. Establishing a National Task Force for Gender Equality Policies 7. Creation of a Public Database of Women Experts

Table 15 UEFISCDI'S inclusive GEP actions

11 SRNSFG's GEP

SNRSFG inclusive new GEP has been elaborated and approved by its administration. The inclusive GEP is foreseen to have a 3-year duration.

The new version of the GEP can be found [here and](#) in the CALIPER project [website](#).

Overall, it includes 7 actions, grouped into the below 4 priority areas

Thematic area	No of Actions
Human Resources	1
Institutional Communication	2
Research funding	3
Transfer to market	1

Table 16 SRNSFG inclusive GEP priority areas

Below a detailed table including each action per thematic area is presented.

Thematic area	Actions
Human Resources	1. Provision of different training and activities improving professional skills
Institutional Communication	2. Organise special targeted events, conference, symposia, e.g in the frame of "Science Fest" 3. Engagement in the creation of Gender mainstreaming platform
Research funding	4. Checking the existence of gender balance in research teams at the project registration stage 5. Establishing award for women scientists 6. Special target call on gender research
Transfer to market	7. WIN event

Table 17 SRNSFG inclusive GEP actions

Concluding remarks

From the analysis of the GEPs presented in the previous chapters, it emerges that the majority of the current versions of GEPs have been approved by the authorities and/or decision-making bodies in charge. The only exceptions are

- ECE NTUA GEP are under the approval process and
- ULB for which their Gender and Diversity Plan incorporating key strategic objectives from the inclusive GEP developed during the project duration is under consultations.

It should be noted that the Horizon Europe GEP eligibility criterion created a more favorable environment for CALIPER's partners with regards to the implementation of the gender equality measures foreseen in their GEPs and in some cases facilitated the approval process of the new GEPs developed by some of the partners, during the final period of the project implementation.

All approved GEPs are published in the project website which will remain updated to include the upcoming approved GEPs. In the project [website](#) all partners have a dedicated sub page including all the relevant material that has been developed during the CALIPER GEP journey.

GEPs that are not approved yet, might be subject to amendments and integration within the approval process, therefore, the actions listed in each GEPs' chapter might not fully correspond to the ones included in the final versions of the documents.

From the above-mentioned chapters, we see that the institutional change processes that have started during the CALIPER project result in embedding key gender equality measures in their everyday institutional practices and working culture and thus pave the way for our partners to be more inclusive institutions (see IRB and YASAR for example).

Overall, the GEPs and the processes and the broad inclusive dialogues which have accompanied their design and approval, show that a change process is triggered and sustained in all RPOs and RFOs.

The areas/topics that have been tackled by CALIPER's partners include Human Resources, Institutional Governance, Institutional Communication, Research, Student services, Teaching, Sexual Harassment and Transfer to Market. In addition, a great majority of our partners continue their collaborations with external stakeholders belonging to their R&I Hub.

